

table). Although *D. angustus* was present in 1979, its number was small. The 1979 population was uniformly distributed along the transect despite large differences between fields in 1978. No heavily infested stems, which might provide evidence of primary infestation from diseased crop residues, were found in any of the fields in 1979. A similar sequence of events was observed at another northerly site between Dacca and Narsingdi.

The nematode overwinters in diseased crop residues and is reactivated by spring rainfall at about the time of sowing — late March and early April.

It appears that the water came too late for ufra in 1979, when there was a spring drought in Bangladesh. The total April rainfall at Joydebpur was 35.5 cm in 1977, 18.0 cm in 1978, but only 1.8 cm in 1979. Matlab Bazar in south Comilla, deep inside the ufra-affected area, had plants exhibiting symptoms of

ufra attack as early as July 1979. The deepwater rice there is sown a few weeks earlier than at Kashimpur as the fields soon become flooded by tidal movements from the river. These observations suggest that spring drought may hinder the northward migration of ufra and that control may be achieved, at least in part, by any procedure that prolongs the winter decay phase by even a few weeks. ■

Effect of length of time after leaf excision on tungro virus source

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When 1,280 adult *Nephotettix virescens* were provided access to tungro-diseased leaves at 0, 2, 4, 8, 24, 48, 72, and 92 hours after excision, the percentage of infective insects varied. The percentage of infective insects gradually decreased as time after excision increased; no insects became infective when access was 96 hours after excision (see figure). But insects were still able to acquire the virus from excised leaves after 72 hours, indicating that partly dried leaves can also serve as a virus source for the insect vector. ■

Effect of time after leaf excision of tungro diseased plant on percentage of infective *Nephotettix virescens*. IRRI.

Sheath rot spreads in Bihar, India

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Sheath rot of rice caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* (revised as *Sarocladium oryzae*) was observed for the first time during 1977 kharif at ARI, Mithapur, Patna, in the National Screening Nursery (NSN) and International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) trials.

The disease had not been reported previously in Bihar. Oblong or somewhat irregular lesions were observed on the uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing the young panicles. Most of the lesions were dark brown, and some had light grey centers. The panicles of some infected tillers emerged only partially. Of 56 IRYN entries, 35 were infected. In 1978, 31.5 of 645 NSN entries at Mithapur farm were infected.

In the 1979 kharif, sheath blight was reported in all four RAU regional research institutes. ■

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Dirty panicles and rice yield reduction caused by bugs

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Species of the rice bugs *Riptortus*, *Stenocoris*, and *Aspavia* attack the rice grain from flowering to harvest and cause considerable crop losses in West Africa. The symptom of bug infestation is grain discoloration, generally described as *dirty panicle*. At Rokupr the feeding behavior of rice bugs and the nature of the damage they cause on rice were studied in 1- × 1- × 1.6-m field cages. *Aspavia* sp. and *Stenocoris* sp. at various densities were caged with the rice varieties CP4 and ROK5 from late booting to harvest. The cages were

checked daily and the different bug densities maintained until harvest. The grains were boiled for 5 minutes in 10% KOH solution; bug damage was then assessed.

Both nymphs and adults attacked the rice grains as soon as the panicle was exerted, and continued to feed on the developing grains until the hard dough stage. The bugs punctured the glumes and sucked the contents of the developing grain. *Riptortus* and *Stenocoris* fed on any site on the grain, but *Aspavia* tended to puncture the grain at the apical end. Only part of the grain milk was removed at each feeding and the same grain could be punctured several times. Fresh signs of *Riptortus* attack were stylet puncture marks, often with milk exudate, on the outer glumes. Those signs were not apparent in attacks